

made at harvest (see table).

Application of SBP reduced disease incidence and percentage of chaffy grains. It increased the number of panicle-bearing tillers and total yield over that in the inoculated control. However, differences among various treatments were not significant. SBP is cheaper than other spray chemicals. One or two 15 kg/ha applications during the rainy season, when it is difficult to spray the crop, may help prevent a secondary spread of the pathogen. ■

Effect of soil-applied stable bleaching powder in controlling bacterial blight of rice, av for 2 years, Ludhiana, India, 1977-78.

Applications (no.)	Disease incidence (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Wt (g) of 1000 healthy grains	Chaffiness (%)	Tillers (no./m ²)	
					With panicles	Without panicles
1	50.8	5.6	28.2	25.8	220.5	68.5
2	49.9	5.6	28.8	25.8	223.0	56.5
3	49.6	5.7	28.9	25.6	234.0	52.0
Control (inoculated)	58.9	5.0	28.8	32.7	215.5	73.5
Control (uninoculated)	9.4	6.4	29.3	15.9	272.0	45.0

A survey of South Arcot District in Tamil Nadu for diseases of rice

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The rice crop on about 230 ha in 8 villages (Vaniyampalayam, Sundaripalayam, V. Akaram, Kurunthipadi, Pennadam, Mazhikaikottam, Eraiyur, and Erappavur) in South Arcot district of Tamil Nadu was surveyed for rice diseases on 13 and

Disease incidence on 4 varieties of rice, Tamil Nadu, India, 1978.

Variety	Tungro (%)	Brown spot (%)	Sheath rot (%)	Narrow brown leaf spot (%)
IR20	56.3	—	43.2	29.6
BCP 1	17.9	—	11.6	3.4
Co 40	90.7	81.5	31.9	5.9
Ponni	35.2	—	17.4	—

14 December 1978. Rice tungro virus disease had the highest incidence,

followed by sheath rot and narrow brown leaf spot (see table). ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Yield loss due to rice tungro virus

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During 1978 kuruvai and samba, a severe incidence of rice tungro virus was observed in Thanjavur district of Tamil Nadu. A study to estimate yield loss caused by the virus was undertaken. The test variety was the highly susceptible ADT 31. Yields from 100 hills that

Yield losses caused by rice tungro virus, Thanjavur district, India, 1978.

Time (DT) ^a when disease symptoms were observed	Grain yield (g/100 hills)	Yield loss (%)
<i>Diseased plants</i>		
15	8.8	98.5
30	14.8	97.2
45	369.6	30.4
60	490.2	7.5
<i>Healthy plants</i>		
	529.7	

^aDays after transplanting.

showed disease symptoms at 15, 30, 45, and 60 days after transplanting were recorded. The yield from 100 healthy hills was also recorded (see table).

During the year severe tungro disease reduced the yield from some of the PES fields to only 450-700 kg/ha. ■

Attraction of gall midge to lights

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A 1978 epidemic of *Orseolia oryzae* on kharif paddy in Chattisgarh region, Madhya Pradesh, is suspected to have been caused by the fact that the summer paddy crop (Jan-Jun) was linked with the kharif season, so gall midge is carried over. About 8% of the tillers of the

preceding summer paddy crop harbored gall midge.

A 100-watt electric bulb was fitted at 2-m height near farmhouse walls at both Raipur and Marod. Swarms of gall midge adults attracted to the lights were then caught by hand net. Times of peak catches at both locations were similar. At Marod 2.1% were caught from 1800 to 1900 hours, 22.5% from 1900 to 2000, 29.8% from 2000 to 2100, 27.5% from 2100 to 2200, and 15.5% from 2200 to 2300 (Fig. 1). The majority (87.4%) of the flies were attracted between 1900 to 2300. After that, the catches declined to 8.3% just before midnight. Thus 97.8% of the flies were attracted and caught before midnight.

Peculiarly, at midnight of 29 September, 98% of the flies were attracted between 2000 and 2100 hours. That night 877,500 flies were collected (Fig. 2). Catches declined the next day. Weather conditions (evening temperature